

The research on the mechanisms and applications of microorganisms and their metabolites in enhancing oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs

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Abstract

Low-permeability reservoirs are characterized by low reservoir permeability and poor fluid mobility, resulting in long-term low recovery efficiency. This necessitates the development of efficient, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly enhanced oil recovery (EOR) technologies. This study focuses on microbial enhanced oil recovery (MEOR) technology, selecting *Bacillus subtilis* BS3096 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* LZ3-2 as model microorganisms to systematically evaluate the functions and mechanisms of their metabolites (lipopeptides and rhamnolipids) in improving oil recovery. Laboratory-simulated imbibition experiments were conducted to explore the critical roles of biosurfactants in reducing oil-water interfacial tension, altering rock wettability, and optimizing imbibition pathways, with comparisons to chemical surfactants. Results showed that lipopeptide biosurfactants significantly reduced the oil-water interfacial tension from 0.8848 mN/m to 0.2055 mN/m and decreased the contact angle from 116.4° to 42.8°, transforming rock wettability from oil-wet to water-wet and increasing oil recovery to 60%, outperforming chemical surfactants. Additionally, microbial cells achieved selective plugging of large pores in cores, directing imbibition fluids toward small pores in low-permeability zones, thereby further enhancing oil displacement efficiency. This study not only highlights the potential application value of microbial metabolites in improving oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs but also provides scientific evidence and technical support for the industrial application of MEOR technology, offering practical insights for the development of efficient, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly EOR techniques.

Keywords

microbial enhanced oil recovery, low-permeability reservoirs, biosurfactants, oil-water interfacial tension, oil recovery efficiency

1. Introduction

Low-permeability reservoirs are an important component of global petroleum resources, characterized by abundant reserves but significant development challenges. Due to their low porosity and poor permeability, crude oil recovery efficiency has remained low over the long term, a problem widely observed worldwide^[1-3]. Traditional enhanced oil recovery (EOR) technologies have improved reservoir development efficiency to some extent; however, their application in low-permeability reservoirs has been limited by high

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costs, energy consumption, and environmental pollution. These technical bottlenecks not only restrict the efficient development and utilization of low-permeability reservoirs but also pose challenges to global energy security. Therefore, the development of a novel, efficient, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly technology to enhance oil recovery has become a core task in the field of low-permeability reservoir research.

In recent years, microbial enhanced oil recovery (MEOR) has gained attention due to its environmentally friendly, economical, and efficient characteristics. MEOR utilizes microorganisms and their metabolites (e.g., biosurfactants) to improve reservoir properties, thereby enhancing oil recovery. Compared with traditional chemical surfactants, biosurfactants can reduce oil-water interfacial tension, optimize wettability, and minimize environmental pollution, enabling green and sustainable development. In low-permeability reservoirs, microorganisms can optimize fluid flow pathways through mechanisms such as selective plugging and imbibition guidance, providing new possibilities for efficient oil recovery [4,5].

Existing studies have demonstrated that microbial metabolites (such as lipopeptides, rhamnolipids, and glycoprotein-based surfactants) effectively reduce oil-water interfacial tension and improve wettability, thereby promoting oil displacement [6,7]. However, the synergistic effects of different microbial strains and their metabolites, as well as their specific mechanisms of action, remain inadequately explored. Thus, investigating the oil recovery mechanisms of microorganisms and their metabolites in low-permeability reservoirs is essential not only to deepen the understanding of MEOR technology but also to provide scientific evidence for its industrial application.

This study focuses on *Bacillus subtilis* BS3096 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* LZ3-2 as model microorganisms, innovatively combining their strains and metabolites to systematically explore their roles and synergistic effects in oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs. Using laboratory-simulated imbibition experiments, this study evaluates the multi-level mechanisms of biosurfactants in reducing interfacial tension, optimizing wettability, and enhancing oil recovery, while systematically comparing their performance with chemical surfactants. The results reveal the oil recovery potential of microbial metabolites and provide new technical pathways for the efficient development of low-permeability reservoirs.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental materials

2.1.1. Microbial strains

This study selected *Bacillus subtilis* BS3096 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* LZ3-2 as model microorganisms. Both strains are capable of producing highly efficient biosurfactants, which play a significant role in enhancing oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs.

Bacillus subtilis BS3096 is a typical producer of lipopeptide biosurfactants. Lipopeptides, composed of amino acids and fatty acids, exhibit excellent interfacial activity and emulsification properties. Under

specific culture conditions, the BS3096 strain efficiently synthesizes lipopeptides. These metabolites not only significantly reduce oil-water interfacial tension but also optimize wettability and improve oil-water distribution, thereby enhancing crude oil displacement efficiency. Consequently, BS3096 is considered a highly promising biosurfactant-producing strain in MEOR technology.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa LZ3-2 is well-known for its efficient production of rhamnolipid biosurfactants. Rhamnolipids, formed by ester bonds between sugar molecules and fatty acid molecules, possess excellent emulsification, dispersion, and interfacial regulation properties. In oil-water systems, rhamnolipids reduce interfacial tension and significantly alter the wettability of rock surfaces, thereby enhancing the mobilization efficiency of crude oil. Under suitable conditions, the LZ3-2 strain produces rhamnolipids efficiently, providing critical technical support for improving oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs.

In summary, these two strains are widely used in MEOR research. This study focuses on their metabolites to systematically explore their roles and mechanisms in enhancing oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs.

2.1.2. Major equipment

This study employed various precise instruments and experimental equipment to evaluate the performance of microbial biosurfactants and their oil recovery effects in simulated reservoir environments. First, the imbibition experimental apparatus is one of the core pieces of equipment used to simulate oil-water flow conditions in low-permeability reservoirs. This apparatus allows precise control of parameters such as pressure, temperature, and permeability, enabling the quantification of the effects of biosurfactants in reservoir pores. Specifically, the apparatus was used to measure key parameters, including oil-water interfacial tension, contact angle, wettability, and recovery efficiency, providing reliable experimental data.

Second, core samples were critical experimental materials used to replicate the pore structures and permeability characteristics of reservoirs. Representative rock samples (e.g., sandstone and carbonate rocks) were selected to simulate the porous media characteristics of low-permeability reservoirs. During the experiments, core samples were immersed in solutions containing biosurfactants to observe the effects of different surfactants on wettability and pore structure and to measure changes in recovery efficiency. Additionally, the surface properties of the core samples (e.g., roughness, porosity, and permeability) significantly influenced the effectiveness of biosurfactants. These parameters were strictly controlled and characterized during the experiments.

Through the combined application of precise experimental equipment and materials, this study comprehensively evaluated the potential of microorganisms and their metabolites to enhance oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs, providing robust experimental evidence for the industrial application of MEOR technology.

2.2. Experimental methods

2.2.1. Microbial cultivation and metabolite extraction

This study optimized the cultivation conditions of *Bacillus subtilis* (BS3096) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (LZ3-2) to maximize biosurfactant production. Optimizing cultivation conditions is critical for the efficient production of microbial metabolites.

- Cultivation medium optimization: To enhance microbial growth efficiency and metabolite yield, a composite medium was selected, and the proportions of components such as carbon sources, nitrogen sources, minerals, and vitamins were adjusted according to the specific requirements of the strains. For instance, the synthesis of lipopeptides and rhamnolipid biosurfactants has stringent requirements for cultivation conditions, including temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen levels. Through a series of optimization experiments, the optimal cultivation conditions for the two strains were determined, ensuring maximum metabolite synthesis efficiency.

- Metabolite extraction: The primary focus of the study was on lipopeptides, rhamnolipids, and glycoprotein metabolites produced during microbial cultivation. After removing cells and residual materials, lipopeptides and rhamnolipids were extracted using a chloroform-methanol solvent system, while glycoproteins were extracted with an aqueous solvent system. The extracts were then concentrated and freeze-dried to obtain high-purity biosurfactants. These purified samples provided reliable materials for subsequent interfacial performance testing and imbibition experiments.

2.2.2. Interfacial performance testing

To systematically evaluate the interfacial activity and oil recovery potential of microbial metabolites, two analytical methods were employed: oil-water interfacial tension measurement and contact angle testing.

- Oil-water interfacial tension measurement: Interfacial tension is a critical parameter for evaluating the performance of surfactants, reflecting their ability to reduce the energy at the oil-water interface. Using a high-precision interfacial tensiometer (e.g., K9-type instrument), the interfacial tension of surfactant solutions at various concentrations was measured, and concentration-interfacial tension curves were plotted to determine the optimal concentration. Additionally, the differences in interfacial tension reduction between lipopeptides and rhamnolipid biosurfactants were compared to comprehensively assess their interfacial activity characteristics.

- Contact angle testing: Wettability is a key indicator of how surfactants alter the physicochemical properties of rock surfaces. A contact angle goniometer was used to analyze changes in the contact angle of oil/water interfaces on rock surfaces. A lower contact angle indicates a transition of the rock surface from oil-wet to water-wet, thereby improving oil recovery. By measuring the extent to which different surfactants improve rock wettability, their effects on crude oil mobilization in reservoirs were evaluated.

2.2.3. Spontaneous imbibition experiments

Spontaneous imbibition experiments were conducted to simulate the oil recovery effects of microbial biosurfactants in low-permeability reservoir rocks and to quantitatively measure the actual recovery rate.

- Surfactant solution preparation: Biosurfactant solutions with different concentrations (e.g., lipopeptides and rhamnolipids) and chemical surfactant solutions were prepared for treating core samples. Experimental conditions (e.g., pressure, temperature, core porosity, and permeability) were set to simulate reservoir environments to ensure data representativeness. By comparing the oil recovery effects of solutions at various concentrations, the optimal concentration range was determined.

- Oil recovery measurement: The oil recovery rate was calculated as the ratio of recovered crude oil to the initial oil content in core samples. Additionally, the crude oil recovery rate at different time points was recorded to analyze the displacement efficiency and mechanisms of the surfactants. For example, lipopeptides exhibited high recovery rates due to their significant ability to reduce oil-water interfacial tension, while rhamnolipids demonstrated advantages in improving wettability.

- Rock pore structure analysis: Using scanning electron microscopy and X-ray computed tomography, the distribution of surfactants within rock pores was observed, and their mechanisms for altering pore structures (e.g., wettability changes or pore clearing) were analyzed. These data further elucidate the critical role of surfactants in improving oil recovery rates.

2.2.4. Surfactant comparison experiments

To compare the performance and oil recovery effects of different types of surfactants, experiments were conducted on biological, anionic, nonionic, and cationic surfactants.

- Biological surfactants: Lipopeptides and rhamnolipids, due to their biodegradability and environmental friendliness, are widely used in EOR. Studies have shown that biological surfactants exhibit high stability under conditions such as low salinity and low temperatures. Their superior interfacial activity and wettability improvement capabilities provided significant advantages in the experiments.

- Chemical surfactants: Anionic surfactants significantly reduce interfacial tension at low concentrations but exhibit poor stability under high salinity and high temperature. Nonionic surfactants have relatively weaker interfacial activity but show strong tolerance to salinity and high temperatures in complex reservoir environments. Cationic surfactants, characterized by excellent emulsification ability, demonstrated potential for oil recovery in specific environments, though their performance is limited under high salinity and high temperature.

- Comparison and evaluation: By comprehensively comparing oil recovery rates and interfacial performance, the experiments highlighted the significant advantages of biological surfactants and analyzed the applicability of various chemical surfactants. The findings provided theoretical support for the optimal selection and combined application of surfactants in low-permeability reservoirs.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analysis of biosurfactant properties

3.1.1. Interfacial performance

This study systematically tested the interfacial performance of lipopeptide biosurfactants produced by *Bacillus subtilis* strain BS3096. The results demonstrated significant potential for EOR through reduced oil-water interfacial tension and improved rock wettability.

Significant reduction in oil-water interfacial tension: The experimental results showed that lipopeptide biosurfactants produced by strain BS3096 could significantly reduce the oil-water interfacial tension from the initial 0.8848 mN/m to 0.2055 mN/m. This indicates that the lipopeptide biosurfactants effectively altered the physicochemical properties of the oil-water interface, reducing interfacial tension and enhancing the displacement efficiency of crude oil in reservoirs. In low-permeability reservoirs, high oil-water interfacial tension is a major factor limiting crude oil mobility and recovery. By significantly lowering interfacial tension, lipopeptide biosurfactants improve the mobility and interaction of the two phases, thereby increasing recovery rates.

Remarkable role in wettability alteration: Additionally, lipopeptide and rhamnolipid biosurfactants demonstrated excellent wettability alteration effects. In spontaneous imbibition experiments, the contact angle on the rock surface decreased significantly from 116.4° to 42.8°, indicating that the biosurfactants successfully transformed the oil-wet state of the rock surface into a water-wet state. Wettability improvement is crucial for enhancing recovery in low-permeability reservoirs because the wettability of the rock directly influences oil-water distribution and crude oil displacement efficiency. Through wettability alteration, the aqueous phase can more effectively displace the oil phase, thereby facilitating crude oil recovery^[8,9].

Geological significance and application potential: These experimental results suggest that lipopeptide and rhamnolipid biosurfactants significantly improve the efficiency of low-permeability reservoir development, particularly in altering reservoir wettability and enhancing crude oil mobility. Compared with the failure risks of traditional chemical surfactants under harsh conditions such as high temperature and high salinity, lipopeptide biosurfactants exhibit stronger salt and temperature resistance, making them suitable for reservoirs with complex geological conditions in oilfield development.

Environmental and sustainable development advantages: As an environmentally friendly and efficient development technology, MEOR holds great promise for secondary and tertiary oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs. The biodegradability of lipopeptide biosurfactants surpasses that of traditional chemical agents, reducing environmental pollution during oilfield development^[10,11]. Therefore, this technology has significant advantages for green and sustainable oilfield development.

From a broader geological perspective, the application of lipopeptide and rhamnolipid biosurfactants provides a new solution for the development of low-permeability reservoirs, helping to increase recovery rates, extend reservoir life, and enhance overall development efficiency. At the same time, the application of

this biotechnology reduces reliance on traditional chemical agents, providing theoretical support and practical pathways for the green transformation of oilfield development.

Exploration and development potential: The experimental results indicate that microbial enhanced oil recovery using lipopeptide and rhamnolipid biosurfactants can significantly improve recovery in low-permeability reservoirs. Against the backdrop of increasing difficulties in reservoir development, the effectiveness of traditional physical and chemical oil displacement techniques has gradually diminished for tight and low-permeability reservoirs. By optimizing microbial cultivation conditions and increasing biosurfactant production, MEOR technology is expected to become a key direction in oilfield development. In the future, this technology could be applied to the development of underutilized complex reservoir resources and play a more prominent role in oilfield development through technological optimization.

3.1.2. Effects of wettability alteration

This study further investigated the role of lipopeptide biosurfactants and rhamnolipids in wettability alteration, particularly their effects on transforming rock surfaces from an oil-wet to a water-wet state. The experimental results showed that lipopeptide biosurfactants produced by *Bacillus subtilis* (BS3096) and rhamnolipids produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (LZ3-2) significantly improved rock wettability, which in turn enhanced spontaneous imbibition oil recovery.

Transformation of rock wettability from oil-wet to water-wet: Contact angle measurements revealed that after treatment with lipopeptide and rhamnolipid biosurfactants, the contact angle of the rock surface decreased significantly from 116.4° to 42.8°, indicating a notable wettability transformation. The mechanism underlying this transformation involves surfactants reducing oil-water interfacial tension and altering the surface energy of the rock, promoting preferential contact between the aqueous phase and the rock surface, displacing the oil phase. After the wettability transition from oil-wet to water-wet, the aqueous phase exhibits stronger wetting on the rock surface, effectively mobilizing crude oil and enhancing spontaneous imbibition efficiency^[12,13]. This wettability alteration provides critical theoretical support for oil recovery technologies.

Improvement of spontaneous imbibition recovery by wettability alteration: The enhancement of wettability has profound implications for the development of low-permeability reservoirs. In such reservoirs, the oil-wet nature of rock surfaces leads to strong adhesion between the oil phase and the rock, making it difficult for the aqueous phase to effectively displace the crude oil. By transforming the rock surface to a water-wet state, lipopeptide and rhamnolipid biosurfactants significantly enhance spontaneous imbibition recovery^[14,15]. Experimental results indicate that the flowability and displacement capacity of the aqueous phase under water-wet conditions increase substantially, making it more effective than traditional techniques in addressing the challenges of low-permeability reservoir development. Therefore, wettability alteration, as a critical supplementary measure, can significantly improve oil recovery rates and has important applications for low-permeability reservoir development.

Geological implications and insights: Rock wettability is a key factor controlling oil recovery, particularly in low-permeability reservoir development, where it directly affects oil-water distribution and crude oil displacement efficiency. Studies have shown that lipopeptide biosurfactants and rhamnolipids can effectively alter rock wettability, transforming oil-wet surfaces into water-wet ones, thereby providing theoretical support and practical guidance for enhancing recovery rates. This wettability alteration not only improves oil displacement efficiency but also reduces energy loss during water flooding, enhancing the economic benefits of oilfield development.

Geological significance: The research on wettability alteration highlights the potential of MEOR technologies in low-permeability reservoir development. As oilfield development shifts toward low-permeability and tight reservoirs, the effectiveness of traditional physical and chemical oil recovery techniques has become increasingly limited. Wettability alteration offers a new technical approach to address these challenges. By applying surfactants such as lipopeptides and rhamnolipids, it is possible to overcome the wettability barriers in low-permeability reservoirs, improve recovery rates, and optimize development strategies. This study has significant implications in the geological field, demonstrating that MEOR not only improves reservoir wettability but also provides new pathways for green and sustainable oilfield development.

Exploration and development potential: The research results provide a new technological pathway for the development of low-permeability reservoirs. Due to the poor permeability of such reservoirs, traditional water injection and chemical flooding methods have limited effectiveness in practice. Wettability alteration, by modifying oil-water distribution, can significantly enhance recovery rates. The application of lipopeptide biosurfactants has shown good field applicability. By further optimizing microbial cultivation conditions and surfactant extraction processes, production yields and performance can be improved. MEOR technology, particularly in enhancing recovery rates, environmental friendliness, and sustainable resource utilization, shows great potential for low-permeability reservoir development. In secondary and tertiary oil recovery stages, this technology is expected to become an important oil recovery method, injecting new momentum into oilfield development.

3.2. Microbial enhanced oil recovery mechanisms

This study explored in detail the mechanisms of MEOR involving lipopeptide biosurfactants produced by *Bacillus subtilis* (strain BS3096) and rhamnolipids produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (strain LZ3-2). The experimental results revealed that the synergistic effects of lipopeptide biosurfactants and microbial cells significantly enhanced the recovery efficiency of low-permeability reservoirs through mechanisms such as interfacial tension reduction, emulsification, and pore structure regulation. The oil recovery rate was improved by up to 60%.

3.2.1. Mechanisms of lipopeptide biosurfactants

Lipopeptide biosurfactants significantly reduce oil-water interfacial tension and enhance emulsification, fundamentally altering the interfacial properties of the two phases. This study demonstrated that lipopeptide biosurfactants reduced the oil-water interfacial tension from 0.8848 mN/m to 0.2055 mN/m, indicating a pronounced interfacial activity. This reduction breaks the strong interfacial forces between oil and water, facilitating the dispersion of crude oil into small droplets and forming stable emulsions. Additionally, lipopeptides modify the wettability of rock surfaces, enhancing the water phase's adhesion to rock surfaces and improving the efficiency of water flooding. Particularly in low-permeability reservoirs, lipopeptide biosurfactants effectively reduce the adhesion of oil phases to rock surfaces, promoting the mobility of crude oil within the water phase and providing a key basis for improved recovery efficiency [16,17].

3.2.2. Role of microbial cells and their effects on pore structure

Beyond the chemical effects of lipopeptide biosurfactants, microbial cells themselves play a crucial role in the MEOR process. The study found that microbial growth within rock cores and the accumulation of their metabolic byproducts selectively blocked large pore regions of the rock, altering fluid flow pathways. Large pore regions, which are typically dominated by water flow due to higher flow rates, are often bypassed by water flooding, leaving smaller pore regions underutilized. Microbial biofilms or cells blocking large pores redirect fluid pathways toward smaller pores, thereby optimizing water flooding routes and significantly improving oil recovery in low-permeability areas. This mechanism provides a new theoretical basis for low-permeability reservoir development, demonstrating that microbial regulation of pore structures is a vital tool for enhanced oil recovery [18,19].

3.2.3. Geological implications and insights

The findings of this study demonstrate the significant geological implications of MEOR technology in the development of low-permeability reservoirs. On one hand, microbial cells and their metabolic products (such as lipopeptide biosurfactants) enhance the mobility and recoverability of crude oil by significantly reducing oil-water interfacial tension and modifying rock wettability, providing technical support for low-permeability reservoir development. On the other hand, microbial cells selectively block pore structures, altering fluid flow pathways, enabling water phases to reach more underdeveloped low-permeability areas. This mechanism significantly improves recovery efficiency and highlights the potential of MEOR technology in optimizing water flooding performance and controlling oil-water distribution. These findings provide innovative strategies for reservoir development.

3.2.4. Geological significance

The geological significance of this study lies in the ability of MEOR technology to overcome the

bottlenecks of low-permeability reservoir development and significantly enhance oil recovery rates. Low-permeability reservoirs, characterized by high oil-water interfacial tension and heterogeneous pore structures, present challenges for conventional water flooding techniques. By introducing MEOR technology, the synergistic effects of lipopeptide biosurfactants and microbial cells can effectively reduce interfacial tension and optimize fluid flow pathways, markedly improving water flooding efficiency. This finding provides a new technical approach for developing low-permeability and tight reservoirs and highlights the broad applicability of MEOR technology in future oilfield development.

3.2.5. Exploration and development potential

Research results indicate that MEOR technology holds significant potential for the exploration and development of low-permeability reservoirs. The dual mechanisms of lipopeptide biosurfactants—reducing interfacial tension and enhancing emulsification—and microbial cells—regulating pore structures and fluid pathways—can significantly improve oilfield recovery rates. Particularly in the secondary and tertiary recovery stages, where water flooding techniques are less effective, MEOR technology offers a promising and innovative approach. Moreover, MEOR technology is environmentally friendly, reducing the ecological impact of chemical flooding techniques and ensuring greater sustainability. This research demonstrates that MEOR technology will play a crucial role in future oilfield development as an effective tool for enhancing recovery rates and optimizing economic benefits, with significant potential for widespread application.

3.3. Comparative analysis of surfactants

This study systematically compared the effects of biosurfactants and chemical surfactants on enhancing oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs. The results indicated that biosurfactants exhibited significantly superior performance, with recovery rates increasing by 11.8% to 41.5% more than chemical surfactants. This difference stems from notable variations in their performance characteristics and environmental adaptability.

3.3.1. Biosurfactants' advantages

Biosurfactants (e.g., lipopeptides and rhamnolipids) demonstrated significant advantages in enhancing oil recovery. The study revealed that using biosurfactants increased recovery rates by 11.8% to 41.5%, outperforming chemical surfactants. This advantage is attributed to the following key factors.

(1) Biosurfactants effectively reduce oil-water interfacial tension and enhance emulsification, thereby altering the interfacial properties of the oil-water system and optimizing water flooding efficiency. Furthermore, biosurfactants promote the wettability alteration of rocks from oil-wet to water-wet, enhancing the utilization of low-permeability reservoirs.

(2) Their natural origin ensures excellent environmental compatibility, providing efficient oil recovery

while minimizing environmental burdens.

(3) Biosurfactants exhibit strong stability under complex geological conditions, particularly maintaining activity in high salinity and high-temperature environments, which greatly enhances their adaptability and application potential in practical oilfield development. These features indicate that biosurfactants have unique advantages in the exploitation of complex low-permeability reservoirs [20,21].

3.3.2. Limitations of chemical surfactants

Although chemical surfactants (e.g., anionic, nonionic, and cationic surfactants) have been widely used in traditional petroleum extraction, their effectiveness in enhancing oil recovery under complex reservoir conditions is limited.

(1) The performance of chemical surfactants is significantly influenced by environmental conditions such as high salinity, high temperature, and extreme pH values. In high-temperature and high-salinity environments, the molecular structure of chemical surfactants may degrade or denature, leading to a substantial decrease in interfacial activity and reduced oil recovery efficiency. For example, high salinity environments can result in chemical surfactants reacting with minerals or other chemical components to form precipitates, which may block pore structures and reduce water flooding efficiency.

(2) The long-term use of chemical surfactants may damage the geological environment of reservoirs, such as inducing water pollution or leaving non-degradable residues. These limitations significantly constrain the practical application potential of chemical surfactants in complex reservoirs [22,23].

3.3.3. Geological significance and implications

The results of this study indicate that biosurfactants have significant geological implications for enhancing oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs. Compared to traditional chemical surfactants, biosurfactants improve the development of complex reservoirs by reducing interfacial tension, optimizing wettability alteration, and enhancing water flooding efficiency. These findings suggest that MEOR, particularly the use of biosurfactant-based approaches, provides a new strategy for reservoir development under complex geological conditions. Additionally, the environmentally friendly nature of biosurfactants offers a more sustainable and eco-friendly oil recovery solution, aligning with the long-term goals of green oilfield development.

3.3.4. Exploration and development potential

Biosurfactants exhibit tremendous potential for application in reservoir exploration and development. Their significant oil recovery enhancement effects and excellent environmental adaptability make them particularly suitable for low-permeability reservoirs, tight reservoirs, and other challenging reservoirs. During secondary and tertiary recovery stages, biosurfactants can serve as an effective auxiliary technology

to enhance water flooding efficiency, reduce development costs, and significantly improve the economic benefits of oilfields. More importantly, the environmental friendliness of biosurfactants helps reduce the ecological damage caused by petroleum extraction, aligning with the sustainable development goals of modern energy exploitation. Therefore, biosurfactants hold broad application prospects in future oilfield development and are expected to become a core technology for improving oil recovery efficiency.

4. Conclusions

(1) Microbial metabolites significantly enhance oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs. This study demonstrated that microbial metabolites, particularly lipopeptide biosurfactants, have a significant effect on enhancing oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs. Experimental results confirmed that lipopeptide biosurfactants effectively reduce oil-water interfacial tension, improve rock surface wettability, and optimize fluid flow paths, thereby significantly enhancing crude oil displacement efficiency and improving recovery rates. Especially in the development of low-permeability reservoirs, these metabolites exhibit excellent oil recovery performance, demonstrating considerable application value and providing reliable technical support for improving the extraction efficiency of complex reservoirs.

(2) *Bacillus subtilis* BS3096 exhibits optimal oil recovery performance. Among the two microorganisms studied, *Bacillus subtilis* BS3096 exhibited the most significant oil recovery performance. The lipopeptide biosurfactants produced by this strain can significantly reduce oil-water interfacial tension while optimizing rock wettability, thereby maximizing recovery rates. Experimental results showed that the lipopeptide products of BS3096 maintain good stability and adaptability under complex geological conditions, exhibiting superior oil recovery performance. These characteristics make BS3096 a preferred technology for improving oil recovery in low-permeability reservoirs, providing a theoretical foundation and practical evidence for the further promotion of MEOR technology.

(3) Biosurfactants demonstrate significant economic and environmental advantages. Compared to chemical surfactants, biosurfactants offer significant advantages in terms of economic efficiency and environmental impact. Biosurfactants not only exhibit outstanding oil recovery performance but also have relatively low production costs and high environmental friendliness. Chemical surfactants are significantly affected by environmental factors such as salinity and temperature, and may cause environmental pollution. In contrast, biosurfactants, with their strong environmental adaptability and stability, can maintain high-efficiency oil recovery performance under complex reservoir conditions such as high salinity and high temperature. Moreover, their natural origin and biodegradability substantially reduce negative environmental impacts. Overall, biosurfactants represent an efficient, economical, and environmentally friendly oil recovery technology with broad promotion and application prospects, offering a sustainable solution for green petroleum extraction.

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